

YORDAN ALGEBRALARI VA ULAR USTIDA UMUMIYLASHTIRILGAN DIFFERENSIALLASHLAR HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Yordan algebralarida umumiy lashtirilgan differensiallash tushunchasi kiritilgan va uning umumiy xossalari o‘rganilgan. Xususan, Yordan algebralarida berilgan umumiy lashtirilgan differensiallashlar yordamida invariantlar qurilgan. Shuningdek, Yordan algebralarida (α, β, γ) -differensiallashlar to‘plamining α, β, γ parametrlarining ayrim qiymatlari bo‘yicha tavsifi keltirilgan.

Kalitso‘zlar. Vektor fazo, Yordan algebrasi, chiziqli akslantirish, differensiallash, umumiy lashtirilgan differensiallash.

1-Ta’rif. Yordan algebrasi J – bu quyidagi ayniyatlarni qanoatlantiruvchi

$$J \times J \rightarrow J$$

Bu chiziqli akslantirish berilgan F maydonidagi V vektor fazosidir

$$a \cdot b = b \cdot a, a, b \in J,$$
$$(a^2 \cdot b) \cdot a = a^2 \cdot (b \cdot a), a, b \in J.$$

Yordan algebralarining (α, β, γ) -differensiallashlari Ta’rifini quyidagicha yozish mumkin.

2-Ta'rif. Aytaylik (J, \cdot) – Yordan algerasi bo'lsin. Chiziqli operator $d \in \text{End}(J)$ J Yordan algebrasining (α, β, γ) – differensiyalashi deb ataladi, agar shunday $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbf{C}$ mavjud bo'lib, barcha $x, y \in J$ elementlar uchun quyidagi shart bajarilsa

$$\alpha d(x \cdot y) = \beta(d(x) \cdot y) + \gamma(x \cdot d(y)).$$

J Yordan algebrasining barcha (α, β, γ) – differensiallashlari to'plamini $\text{Der}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}(J)$ orqali belgilaylik. Ushbu to'plam quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$\text{Der}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}(J) = \{d \in \text{End}(J) : \alpha d(x \cdot y) = \beta(d(x) \cdot y) + \gamma(x \cdot d(y)), x, y \in J\}.$$

Bu yerda $\text{Der}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}(J)$ to'plam $\text{End}(J)$ ning vektor qism fazosi bo'ladi.

Teorema. J – birlik elementli Yordan algebrasi va $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbf{F}$ bo'lsin. U holda $\text{Der}_{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}(J)$ vektor fazo quyidagi ko'rinishlarga ega bo'ladi.

1. $\text{Der}_{(1,1,1)}(J) = \text{Der}(J)$, bu yerda $\text{Der}(J)$ – bu J Yordan algebrasining barcha differensiallashlari Li algebrasi;

2. $\text{Der}_{(1,1,0)}(J) \subseteq \text{End}(L)$ va $\text{Der}_{(1,1,0)}(J)$ to'plamni J Yordan algebrasining barcha idempotent elementlari to'plami $\text{Id}(J)$ bilan

$$p \in \text{Id}(J), \quad d(x) = p \cdot x, \quad x \in J$$

orqali aynan tenglashtirish mumkin.

3. $\text{Der}_{(1,1,-1)}(J) \subseteq \text{Der}_{(1,0,0)}(J) \equiv 0.$

4. $\text{Der}_{(0,1,1)}(J) \equiv 0.$

5. $\text{Der}_{(0,1,-1)}(J)$ to'plamni $Z_o(J) = \{a \in J \mid (b \cdot a) \cdot c = b \cdot (a \cdot c), b, c \in J\}$ to'plam bilan

$$a \in Z_o(J), \quad d(x) = a \cdot x, \quad x \in J.$$

orqali aynan tenglashtirish mumkin.

6. $\text{Der}_{(0,1,0)}(J) \equiv 0;$

7. Agar $\delta \neq 1$ bo'lsa, u holda $\text{Der}_{(\delta,1,0)}(J) \equiv 0.$

Teorema isboti. $d(x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y, x, y \in J$ tenglikdan $d(x) = d(e) \cdot x, x \in J$ tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. U holda, J Yordan algebrasi kommutativ bo‘lgani uchun

$$d(x \cdot y) = d(e) \cdot (x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y = d(y) \cdot x, \quad x, y \in J$$

va

$$d(x \cdot y) = d(x \cdot e) \cdot y = (d(e) \cdot x) \cdot y = (d(e) \cdot y) \cdot x, \quad x, y \in J.$$

Bundan $d(e)$ – bu markaziy elementdir. Shu bilan birga

$$d(e) = d(e \cdot e) = d(e) \cdot d(e),$$

ya’ni $d(e)$ element idempotent elementdir. Aksincha, J Yordan algebrasining har qanday markaziy idempotenti p uchun

$$d(x) = p \cdot x, \quad x \in J,$$

akslantirish $Der_{(1,1,0)}(J)$ to‘plamga tegishli va shu yo‘l bilan $Der_{(1,1,0)}(J)$ to‘plamni J Yordan algebrasining barcha idempotent elementlari to‘plami bilan aynan tenglashtirish mumkin.

Bundan esa 1 va 2 ko‘rinishlarning bajarilishi ravshandir.

3. Ta’rifga ko‘ra $Der_{(1,1,-1)}(J) = \{d \in End(J) \mid d(x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y - x \cdot d(y), x, y \in J\}$. Quyidagi tengliklar o‘rinli

$$d(x) = d(e) \cdot x - d(x), \quad x, y \in J,$$

$$d(x \cdot y) = (d(e) \cdot x - d(x)) \cdot y - x \cdot (d(e) \cdot y - d(y)) =$$

$$(d(e) \cdot x) \cdot y - d(x) \cdot y - x \cdot (d(e) \cdot y) + x \cdot d(y) =$$

$$(d(e) \cdot x) \cdot y - x \cdot (d(e) \cdot y) - d(x \cdot y), \quad x, y \in J,$$

$$d(e) = d(e \cdot e) = d(e) \cdot e - e \cdot d(e) = 0.$$

Bundan

$$d(x \cdot y) = -d(x \cdot y) = 0, \quad x, y \in J$$

va

$$d(e \cdot x) = -d(e \cdot x) = d(x) = 0, \quad x \in J.$$

Oxirgi tenglikdan ko‘rinadiki $Der_{(1,1,-1)}(J) \equiv 0$.

4. Ta‘rifga ko‘ra, $Der_{(0,1,1)}(J)$ to‘plam quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$Der_{(0,1,1)}(J) = \{d \in \text{End}(J) \mid d(x) \cdot y = -x \cdot d(y), x, y \in J\}.$$

U holda $d(e) \cdot x = -e \cdot d(x) = -d(x)$, $x \in J$, $d(e) \cdot e = -e \cdot d(e)$, $d(e) = 0$. Bundan

$$d(x) = e \cdot d(x) = -d(e) \cdot x = 0, \quad x \in J.$$

Demak, $Der_{(0,1,1)}(J) \equiv 0$.

5. Yuqoridagidek, $Der_{(0,1,-1)}(J) = \{d \in \text{End}(J) \mid d(x) \cdot y = x \cdot d(y), x, y \in J\}$ to‘plam uchun quyidagi tengliklarni hosil qilish mumkin

$$d(e) \cdot x = e \cdot d(x) = d(x), \quad x \in J,$$

$$d(x) \cdot y = (d(e) \cdot x) \cdot y = (x \cdot d(e)) \cdot y = x \cdot d(y) = x \cdot (d(e) \cdot y), x, y \in J.$$

Endi

$$Z_o(J) = \{a \in J \mid (b \cdot a) \cdot c = b \cdot (a \cdot c), b, c \in J\}$$

to‘plamdan ixtiyoriy $a \in Z_o(J)$ element olamiz. Quyidagi

$$d(x) = a \cdot x, \quad x \in J.$$

akslantirish $Der_{(0,1,-1)}(J)$ to‘plamga tegishli ekanini ko‘rsatamiz. Haqiqatan ham,

$$d(x) \cdot y = (a \cdot x) \cdot y = (x \cdot a) \cdot y = x \cdot (a \cdot y) = x \cdot d(y), \quad x, y \in J.$$

6. Ta‘rifga ko‘ra, $Der_{(0,1,0)}(J)$ to‘plam quyidagicha aniqlanadi

$$Der_{(0,1,0)}(J) = \{d \in \text{End}(J) \mid d(x) \cdot y = 0, x, y \in J\}.$$

Quyidagi tengliklar o‘rinli

$$d(x) = d(x) \cdot e = 0, \quad d(e) = d(e) \cdot e = 0, \quad x \in J.$$

Bundan $Der_{(0,1,0)}(J) \equiv 0$.

7. Nihoyat, oxirgi

$$Der_{(\delta,1,0)}(J) = \{d \in \text{End}(J) \mid \delta d(x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y, x, y \in J\}$$

to‘plam quyidagi tengliklarni hosil qilish mumkin

$$\delta d(x) = \delta d(x \cdot e) = d(x) \cdot e = d(x), \quad x \in J$$

$$\delta d(x) = d(x), \quad (\delta - 1)d(x) = 0, \delta \neq 1, d(x) = 0 \quad x \in J.$$

Chunki

$$0 = (\delta - 1)^{-1}0 = (\delta - 1)^{-1}(\delta - 1)d(x) = d(x).$$

Demak, $Der_{(\delta,1,0)}(J) \equiv 0$.

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